

Income of Chicken KUB Business in Flores Bajawa Agricultural College

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ABSTRACT: Balitbangtan's superior native chicken (KUB) is a non-racial chicken that can produce meat and eggs, egg production from KUB chickens is quite a lot can reach 50% per day. This KUB chicken is the result of research by the Livestock Research Agency-Agricultural Research and Development Agency and licensed to PT. ayam Kampung Indonesia (AKI) or more precisely obtained from the results of crossing and then widely developed. Kampung chicken business is generally cultivated by small farmers in rural areas as a side business. But in this way, the profit of farmers is very small, because the business has not led to commercial businesses. Superior local chicken business with good professional management can increase the economic value of farmers more optimally. The local chicken business can continue to be cultivated by small farmers in rural areas, although the scale of maintenance is still low. This research was conducted for approximately one month, starting in June-July 2024. The research location was at the Flores College of Agriculture in Bajawa. The college is engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry. The population of poultry raised at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture is 600 birds. The data analyzed in this study are primary data taken directly from the research location. The income from the KUB chicken business raised at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture during one maintenance period received a significant profit of approximately 65%. Of course this is inseparable from good maintenance management patterns so that it has an impact on the benefits obtained. In addition, the cage / cage employees of course also pay attention to the health of KUB chickens so as to emphasize the high mortality rate of chickens.

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INTRODUCTION

According to data from the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), the consumption of broiler or native chicken meat in Indonesia in 2021 was 0.14 kilograms (kg) per capita per week, an increase of 9.23% compared to 2020 which was 0.13 kg. The trend of chicken meat consumption per capita in Indonesia also tends to increase from 2011-2021. The highest growth occurred in 2014 by 19.77% from 0.09 kg to 0.10 kg per week (BPS, 2022). The average consumption of purebred or free-range chicken eggs in Indonesia in 2022 was 2.336 kg per capita per week. This figure increased by 2.45% compared to the previous year which amounted to 2.28 kg per capita per week (BPS 2023).

Balitbangtan Seeded Kampong Chicken (KUB) is one type of non-race chicken that can be taken meat and eggs as a production product. KUB chickens are the product of research conducted by the Livestock Research Institute - Agricultural Research and Development Agency since 1997 and have been licensed to PT Ayam Kampung Indonesia (AKI) to be developed to produce superior layer and broiler *final stock* products (BPTP Yogyakarta 2013). The advantages of KUB *parent stock* are shorter brooding time with 84% hatchability, high egg production of ± 180 grains per year. The body weight produced by KUB chickens ranges from 800 - 1000 gr during 10 weeks of maintenance, when compared to the weight of ordinary native chickens, the growth of KUB chickens to reach maximum weight takes 16 - 20 weeks.

The native chicken business is generally practiced by small farmers in rural areas as a side business. However, in this way, the profit of farmers is very small, because the business has not yet led to a commercial business. Superior local chicken business with good professional management can increase the economic value of farmers more optimally. The native chicken business can continue to be cultivated by small farmers in rural areas, although the scale of maintenance is still low (Amri et al., 2017).

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The raising of broiler KUB chickens is expected to be developed by the community into a source of income, but an innovation can be accepted and developed if the level of marketing and production income is high in real economic improvement from previous conditions. This study aims to determine the income and development of broiler KUB chicken cultivation assisted by Balitbang (Adawiyah, 2017).

The reason for researching the income of the KUB chicken business at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture is because it sees that the business has been running for quite a long time, but no one has conducted research at that location with a commodity on poultry or KUB chickens. KUB chicken cultivated at STIPER is a business developed by the university to fulfill the requirements as one of the universities engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry for students to practice, besides that the level of demand for native chicken by the people of Ngada Regency is quite high if it is percented to reach 80% but the supply of native chicken is quite limited, therefore the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture cultivates the native chicken business. For this reason, researchers are interested in conducting research on the income of the KUB chicken business.

The income obtained by the farmer will vary according to the level of the farmer's ability to allocate the factors it has including the number of DOC, feed, labor, vaccines, drugs, vitamins, heaters and mortality. Farmers must be able to manage these production factors so that maximum production can be achieved. In this case, the researcher conducted a study entitled Marketing and Income of KUB Chicken Business at Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture.

RESEARCH METHODS

Time and Place

This research was conducted for approximately one month starting from June-July 2024. The research location was at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture. The reason for taking the research location in this place is because the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture has a livestock business, namely from ruminants to poultry, one of which is KUB chicken. Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture is a college that is engaged in agriculture and animal husbandry. The population of poultry raised at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture is 600 birds.

Data Collection Method

Data collection was done directly by conducting interviews with resource persons at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture, documentation and noting important things conveyed by resource persons and taking primary data (recording during the maintenance period) owned by the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture. The data taken is about the business income of KUB chickens cultivated at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analyzed in this study are primary data taken directly from the research location. The data obtained were analyzed using descriptive quantitative methods. The data obtained is used to calculate:

1. Fixed cost (TC)

To find out the costs used in the broiler breeding business using the formula:

$$TC = TFC + TVC$$

Description:

TC = Total Cost

TFC = Total Fixed Cost

TVC = Total Variable Cost

2. Acceptance (TR) To determine the acceptance of broiler breeders, the following formula is used (Soekartawi, 2003):

$$\text{Total Revenue (TR)} = P_y \times Y$$

Description:

TR = Total Revenue (Rp/Year)

P_y = Product Price

Y = Total Production

3. Income To determine the income of broiler farmers, the following formula is used (Soekartawi, 2003):

$$\text{Total Revenue (Pd)} = TR - TC$$

Where :Pd = Total income earned by farmers (Rp / Year)

TR = Total Revenue / revenue obtained by farmers (Rp / year)

TC= Total Cost/Costs incurred by farmers (Rp/year)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Production Cost

Production costs are also known as expenditure costs. Included in the production costs in this study are the cost of purchasing seeds, the cost of feed, the cost of purchasing drinking water, the cost of electricity, the cost of making buildings or cages, the cost of equipment, the cost of medicines and vaccines, the cost of paying taxes. In this case, it is in accordance with the

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opinion of (Ngaku, et al., 2020) that production costs include land costs, equipment depreciation costs, and family labor costs. While variable costs include cocoa plant maintenance costs, and other costs incurred in one business cycle. This is in line with the opinion of (Ngaku, et al., 2024) on production costs divided into two, namely fixed costs and non-fixed costs. Fixed costs are costs incurred only once in the production process such as building costs, tax costs, depreciation, equipment, machinery and labor. Non-fixed costs are costs that are incurred continuously such as the cost of purchasing feed, purchasing medicines and vitamins, water costs, electricity costs. In more detail related to the details of the costs incurred, contained in appendix 1.

Production costs incurred in one period of KUB chicken production amounted to Rp 22,240,000. From the data, it can be explained that the cost of purchasing seeds / DOC KUB chickens is 6 boxes with 600 DOC chickens at a price per box of Rp 9,900,000. The KUB chickens that were cultivated at the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture in June-July 2024 for one period (for four months) were 600 chickens. But on the way there were about 65 birds that died. From the data, it can be seen that the *mortality* rate (death) is 0.10%, it can be known that the chicken mortality rate is quite normal. This can also be suspected due to a less conducive environment and maintenance management that is still less consistent, causing stress in chickens and resulting in death in chickens. The number of live chickens was 535.

Mortality Formula = Number of dead chickens x 100% / number of initial chickens

Feed spent during the period of raising KUB chickens from DOC to harvest spent approximately 15 sacks of feed at a price of Rp 6,720,000. The cost of purchasing medicines during the maintenance period is Rp 120,000. the cost of purchasing 1 package of vitamins is Rp 250,000. Drinking water spent approximately 3 cans with the price per can is as much as IDR 100,000 and in the maintenance period spent approximately 3 cans with a total of IDR 300,000, electricity costs IDR 450,000, labor costs of 1 person for 4 months IDR 4,000,000, transportation costs IDR 500,000.

Reception

Revenue is the total income obtained from the sale of goods produced. The goods in question here are KUB chickens. This is in accordance with the opinion according to (Anshory et al., 2020) Revenue is obtained from multiplying the amount of production by the selling price of the product. The amount of revenue received by farmers is influenced by the amount of production produced in the farm production unit. The more production produced, the greater the revenue from the farm. Conversely, the lower the amount of production, the smaller the revenue on the farm (Ngaku, et al., 2024).

The amount of revenue received by Flores Bajawa Agricultural College amounted to Rp 53,500,000. The revenue was obtained from the sale of KUB chickens with a selling price/head of IDR 100,000, with a total of 353 live chickens. The revenue is still in the form of gross revenue which has not been reduced by production costs during the maintenance period.

Revenue

Income is the result of revenue minus expenses. This means that the revenue from selling chickens is reduced by the production costs during the maintenance period. According to (Ngaku, et al., 2024) the profit or income of farmers is the amount of money received by farmers from the reduction of production costs incurred within a certain period of time. By looking at the amount of income received by farmers, we can find out whether a farm is profitable or even a loss.

The total income earned by the Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture during one rearing period was IDR 31,260,000. From these results it can be seen that the KUB chicken business is certainly profitable. The benefits obtained are certainly inseparable from the aspect of good maintenance, consistent feeding, drinking water and also incentive care so that it is cumulative to income. (Sugiarto, Fentih, and Novianti, 2014) stated that differences in farm profits are caused by a number of factors, including business size, product sales costs, production costs, and long market chains, environment, climate, and farm maintenance. This is in line with the views and income of Novianti (2014), which states that differences in income are caused by farmers by several things including differences in the scale of the business, the selling price of each product, the price of production facilities, and intensive policies set by the company, climate, weather, and maintenance. maintenance.

CONCLUSION

The income from the KUB chicken business during the maintenance period is profitable. This is certainly inseparable from good maintenance and management patterns so that it has an impact on the benefits obtained. The suggestion that the researcher wants to convey is for students who are doing practicals and supervisors who are guiding the need for special direction for students in managing the cage and the maintenance process and also of course paying attention to the health of KUB chickens so as to emphasize the high mortality rate of chickens. In addition, it is also necessary to pay attention to the environmental conditions around, because chickens are poultry that are easily stressed.

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Table 1. production and business costs of KUB chickens at Flores Bajawa College of Agriculture in June, 2024.

No.	Material name	Price (Rp)	Unit (Item)	Total
1	Chicken seedlings/DOC KUB	1.650.000	6 boxes (100 pieces)	9.900.000
2	Feed	6.720.000	15 sacks	6.720.000
3	Purchase of medicines	120.000	1 package	120.000
4	Vitamins	250.000	1 package	250.000
5	Drinking water	100.000	3 cans	300.000
6	Electricity	450.000	4 months	450.000
7	Labor cost	1.000.000	4 months	4.000.000
8	Transportation costs	500.000	-	500.000
Total				22.240.000
8	Reception	100,000/Ekor	353 tails	53.500.000
9	Income (revenue-production cost)	53.500.000- 22.240.000	-	31.260.000

Source: Primary data processed, 2024